

THE ROLE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN PHYSICS-RELATED TEACHING OF BIOLOGY**Mehdiyeva Sevinj Nizami***Faculty of Chemistry and Biology, teacher
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The article notes that connecting Project-based learning with life processes not only improves the course quality, but also demonstrates the close relationship between biology and physics, creates a complete image of natural phenomena in students, and increases their interest in the learning process. The use of projects with interdisciplinary content plays a major role in deepening the concepts learned by the relevant sciences, preventing the repetition of the same material in different disciplines, in a complex approach to studying interconnected phenomena, and other issues.

Keywords: biology, interdisciplinarity, physics, osmosis, experience

It is possible to take a complex approach to studying biology and physics, use the laws and phenomena of science in detail in the process of studying another science, and expand interdisciplinary communication via project-based learning.

Integration with physical science is of great importance to obtain a complete image of the processes in living organisms. For example, a complex physiological process such as blood circulation involves hydrodynamic processes related to fluid flow, mechanical processes characterized by work, thermodynamic processes on heating, and electrodynamic processes providing the generation and propagation of nerve impulses. An endless number of facts may be shown about how living organisms adapt their life and activities to physics laws. For example, atmospheric pressure and diffusion phenomena play the main role in the lives of both humans and animals. Respiration and nutrition processes, heart function, the absorption process (drinking, eating), adhesion of worms to the intestinal wall, leech feeding are integrated with diffusion and atmospheric pressure. Simultaneously, in humans and animals, oxygen gets into the body and tissues, carbon dioxide gets rid of from the tissues to the lungs, and removed from there by the pressure difference. As we know, amoeba's nutrition and respiration occur through a single cell. Its cytoplasm and nucleus are covered by a semipermeable membrane. The membrane is porous, with high liquid viscosity on one side and low on the other. More precisely, oxygen or nutrients in the environment outside the membrane is more, and less in the inner membrane (cytoplasm). In this case, if the liquid inside the amoeba is thicker than the liquid surrounding, the water and oxygen dissolved in the water pass into the membrane covering the entire surface of the amoeba. The amount of other gases (carbon dioxide) inside the amoeba is more than in the external environment. In this case, those gases are released from inside the partition to the outside environment. Thus, the amoeba, a single-celled animal, respire. This process continues day and night. The main function of the collapsible bladder is to move the amoeba out of the outer membrane as a result of osmotic pressure. The amoeba surrounds its feeding by forming false legs. The nutrients entering the cytoplasm are covered with

digestive juice (saliva) and a digestive cyst forms. Digestive enzymes diffuse into it from the cytoplasm. Nutrients in the digestive tract are digested by the cell (amoeba) as a result of osmosis and diffusion. The digestive bladder containing undigested food approaches the body surface of the amoeba and is removed from the body by reason of osmotic pressure. That is, the bladder gradually grows, when reaching a certain volume, bursts and is expelled due to the difference in osmotic pressure. Then a new cycle continues in that area and forms a new drop. This process is repeated periodically. Furthermore, water, nutrients, and oxygen enter the amoeba from the environment through the osmotic pressure of the outer membrane. The viscosity of various nutrients dissolved in the amoeba is higher than the viscosity of fresh water. So, an osmotic pressure difference is observed between the outside of the amoeba and the surrounding environment. The opening and closing bladder performs the function of regulating the osmotic pressure, removing the rest of the metabolic nutrients with water to the external environment.

Although osmosis is a simple water exchange in cells, osmosis is the basis of important complex processes in many living things (mainly plants). This is one of the most difficult topics for students to perceive in the school curriculum. So, a correctly chosen experiment is of great importance to understand the osmosis phenomenon. Project topics connecting with the osmosis phenomenon in biology teaching may be attributed to projects with interdisciplinary content.

The experiment used allows students to observe the osmosis phenomenon and even make measurements. For this, simple materials are required: acetic acid, hypotonic solution - boiled water, hypertonic solution - jam juice, raw eggs - 2, glass - 3, gloves, scales, marker, spectacles. No hazardous substances are used during the experiment. However, recommended to use gloves and protective spectacles just in case. Students may be allergic to acetic acid, or acetic acid may accidentally splash into the eye. If acetic acid splashes into the eyes, recommended to wash with plenty of water. The experiment consists of the following phases: [1]

Phase I:

- 2 raw eggs are taken and both are placed inside the glass;
- Acetic acid is added to the glass (until covering the eggs);
- The eggs should remain in the acetic acid for up to three days (It may be observed how the acetic acid dissolves the eggshell over time).

Phase II:

- The shelled eggs are washed with water, weighed on a scale and their mass is noted.
- Eggs are placed in separate glasses.
- A hypotonic solution (boiled water) is added to one of the glasses, and a hypertonic solution (jam juice) to the other.

You may note the name of the solution on the glasses with a marker. This allows students to visually see the names of the solutions and remember better.

The eggs should remain in the solution for at least 8 hours. You may clearly observe how the volume of the egg in the hypotonic solution increases, while the egg in the hypertonic solution shrinks.

Phase III:

- The eggs are reweighed on the scale and the initial and subsequent masses are compared.

Jam juice, natural fruit juices, honey, jelly (grape syrup), various syrups may be used as a hypertonic solution. In this case, adding additional water to the jam water isn't required, otherwise, the osmosis process will take place later. You may use any acetic acid in your kitchen. You should be a little careful when using the extract, as it is thicker, and may destroy the lower membrane of the egg, consequently, the integrity of the egg may be compromised. In this case, shortening the waiting period (about 2 days) is required. At the end of the project, the conclusion of the experiment is submitted.

Solution	Before	After
Hypertonic solution (jam juice)	97	71
Hypotonic solution (boiled water)	85	94

Based on such facts, connecting the project topics with life processes improves the quality of the lesson and demonstrates the close connection between natural sciences, creates a more complete image of natural phenomena in students, gradually increases their interest in the learning process. Additionally, understood that studying all these features in detail allows for revealing the physico-chemical mechanisms in the nature of biological processes, creating changes in the desired direction in creatures through the physical effects of the environment.

References

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